

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND TOOLS

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Abstract: This article talks about "Methods and tools of education" and provides information about the practical importance of methods, types, methods of use and tools. The practical significance of the methods is discussed in detail.

Key words: Method, educational methods, educational tool, didactic tools, methods of organizing activities and forming (exercise) norms of behavior, methods of training and teaching, methods of stimulating and motivating activities .

The word method is a Greek word that means research, a way to achieve a goal, a method. A method - in the most general sense - is a method of achieving a goal, an activity organized in a certain way. The main content of the methods is scientific theories tested in practice. Any scientific theory essentially has a method function. The method, in turn, becomes a tool for the discovery of new scientific theories and laws.

Educational methods are understood as a set of methods of organizing the teaching work of the teacher and students' learning activities in order to solve various didactic tasks aimed at mastering the studied material. Educational methods first appear in the pedagogue's mind in the form of a general project of activity in a certain direction. This project is put into practice as a set of specific actions, actions or methods aimed at the interaction of teacher and student activities, teaching and learning. The method does not appear in other forms, because of this, the educational method represents the didactic model of activity in general. In didactics, the term educational methods is also widely used.

The educational method means the joint activities of the teacher and students aimed at achieving the expected goal in the educational process. Teaching methods determine the activity of the teacher and student in the educational process, how to organize and conduct the teaching process. Educational method is a component or separate aspect of an educational method. Methods and method relations are interconnected. Method and method are connected to each other as a whole and a part. Only part of the pedagogical or educational task is solved with the help of methods.

Some teachers use the concept of "style" instead of the concept of "method". But the concept of "style" cannot fully reflect the essence of the term "method". Because the method has a more specific (in this case, it expresses the specificity of the teacher) description and cannot serve as a way to achieve a specific goal.

Didactic studies show that the nomenclature (naming) and classification of educational methods are very different depending on the chosen approach to their development. We will focus on the most important of them. So, educational methods are classified as follows:

1. Traditional educational methods: oral, visual, practical, working with books and video methods.
2. Educational methods according to the description of students' cognitive activity: Information-receptive, reproductive, problem statement, heuristic (partial search), research.
3. Educational methods according to the main didactic goals:
 - a) acquisition of new knowledge;
 - b) formation of skills and qualifications;
 - d) applying knowledge in practice.
4. Educational methods according to the holistic approach:
 - a) methods of strengthening and control of knowledge, skills and qualifications;
 - b) methods of organizing and implementing educational activities;
 - d) methods of motivating and stimulating educational activities;
 - c) methods of control and self-control of educational activities.
5. Interactive methods and graphic organizers.
 - a) methods of encouraging students to learn;
 - b) methods of understanding new material;
 - d) methods that allow thinking about what has been learned.

Demonstration methods are also of special importance in ensuring the quality and efficiency of education.

Although the image (illustration) method is closely related to the demonstration method, it is studied separately in didactics. Illustration requires the representation of things, events and processes with the help of their symbolic representations - drawings, pictures, photographs, flat models, etc.

The demonstration method is useful in revealing the dynamics of the studied object, and at the same time, it is widely used to provide complete information about the external appearance and internal structure of the object. When presenting natural objects, attention is usually paid to its external appearance (shape, size, quantity, color, parts, their mutual relations), and then to the study of its internal structure or special features. Demonstration is often observed using a subject or a drawing of the object being studied.

Practical method - requires the application of acquired knowledge in a process aimed at finding solutions to practical problems. In this, the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice is formed. Practical work is carried out in the classroom or in natural conditions - school grounds, greenhouses, geographical areas. The actions taken during their implementation are monitored by the teacher and, in necessary cases, the instruction or special instruction is brought to the attention of the students.

Educational methods are used together with educational tools. Educational tools are objects used by teachers and students to acquire new knowledge. Educational tools are very important. All means of education successfully implement educational goals. Educational tools reflect the material or spiritual values necessary to achieve educational goals. Usually, they are used in accordance with educational methods. However, if methods answer the question of "how to teach", tools answer the question of "what to teach with it". The traditionally used educational tools include textbooks, pictures, tables, speech, educational-workshop equipment,

laboratories, information media, tools for organizing and managing the educational process.

Didactic tools mean educational and demonstration manuals, demonstration devices, and technical tools. Didactic tools, like methods, perform an educational, educational and developmental function. In addition, he performs the tasks of creating, managing and controlling students' educational activities. Didactic tools perform motivational, informational, educational process management and optimization functions in audiovisual detail.

Choosing an educational tool is related to choosing an educational method. If the active method of education (working with books, exercises) is used, then training manuals, textbooks and technical means of education are used. Active and technical means of education are used in practical methods.

The classification of educational tools cannot be clear and uniform. The important part of the educational tool is that they are used together and are never mutually exclusive. The task of the teacher is to choose an effective means of education to activate the learning process. The classification of educational tools can be approached according to different bases:

- according to the subject of activity;
- according to the object of activity;
- in relation to educational information;
- according to the task in the educational process.

The correct choice of the teaching method by the teacher, the explanation of the topic using various tools during the lesson helps to increase the quality of education. As it has been mentioned many times above, as a result of combining educational

methods with the method of a qualified teacher, the content and peculiarities of science and the studied subject are fully revealed. This serves as a basis for the formation and development of students' knowledge, skills, and competences in science.

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